

More robust offshore wind energy planning through model ensembling

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Abstract

This research performs an *ex-ante* assessment of the 19 high potential areas for offshore wind energy (HPA-OWE) allocated in four maritime spatial planning regions of Spain. A 39 geo-statistical criteria pool was developed and categorized into five planning tiers: co-existence, socio-ecological, spatial-efficiency, energy equity and technical/technological tier. An ensemble of three multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) techniques coupled with a Monte Carlo method based on a large, uniform number of randomly distributed criteria weights creates more robust priority rankings for HPA-OWE planning in the context of maritime spatial planning (MSP). Overall results of the co-existence tier indicate HPA-OWE should be prioritized in the North Atlantic (NOR1 and 4) and in the Levantine-Balearic (LEBA3 and 2) planning subdivision. The application of Machine Learning on the MCDA results allowed to identify criteria that most influence the score of each HPA-OWE and at planning subdivision scale. The outcomes highlighted the urgent need to include place-based data to better take into account spatial inequalities from declining/deindustrialized coastal regions and re-balance them with socio-economic and energetically privileged coastal territories. The performed *ex-ante* analysis provides essential insights for new generation maritime spatial plans and for testing of planning hypotheses related to large offshore infrastructure.

Introduction

Offshore wind energy (OWE) development belongs to the pillars of the European¹ and global Energy transition². In European seas, national governments have identified potential areas for offshore wind energy deployment using Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP). Most recent national MSP initiatives lack the analytical tools necessary to provide *ex-ante* assessments for sea areas prioritized for offshore wind energy (OWE) development. *Ex-ante* assessments are crucial as they support decision-making in the early stages of developing technological systems, facilitating the sustainable deployment of infrastructure and technological innovations^{3,4}. *Ex-ante* assessments of maritime spatial plans are a priority area for the European Maritime, Fishery and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF) and have the benefit of identifying trade-offs, minimize conflicts, promote sustainable development in marine areas and reinvigorate with new knowledge future amendments and cycles of national maritime spatial plans. In the context of OWE planning, MSP appears to have multiple utilities, such as ensuring legal certainty of use of the sea space of emerging human activities such as OWE⁵, it regulates co-existence of OWE with existing human activities at sea (commercial fishery, shipping, aquaculture, etc...)⁶, it fosters ecosystem-based management of natural resources at multi-sectoral level⁷ and facilitates coordinated actions among stakeholders.

However, MSP, together with the Blue Economy - which encompasses economic activities that depend on the sea, often associated with other economic sectors, including tourism, maritime transport, energy and fishing⁸ - receives increased criticism together with Blue Economy, because promoting a neoliberal logic centred on re-spatializing the sea space in favour of economic interests⁹, leaving behind nature protection and the place-based socio-cultural characteristics of coastal territories^{10,11}.

52 European seas are experiencing significant changes in governance, particularly through the
53 implementation of the MSP Directive. As of January 2018, 21 out of 23 EU member states
54 have transposed the MSP Directive into their national legislation¹². The pressing need for
55 transitioning towards more sustainable modes of energy production is expected to increase
56 competition for sea space of up to 80% of Europe's sea space by 2050¹³ for marine wind
57 energy deployment. The experience of first-cycle national maritime spatial plans provides an
58 unprecedented opportunity to initiate *ex-ante* assessments addressing the balance of
59 ecological, social, spatial, economic, energy-related, and technological characteristics when
60 determining the allocation of OWE arrays at sea.

61 Literature on MSP has identified in multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA)^{14–17} a central
62 technique for offshore wind energy allocation. In the last five years the approach has been
63 subjected to an evolution as techniques shifted from single to ensembled MCDA
64 (EnseMCDA) techniques^{14,18}. Ensembling techniques involve the aggregation of multiple
65 decision-making methods, criteria, or models to rank alternatives across multiple objectives.
66 They leverage the strengths of individual methods, compensate for their weaknesses, and
67 provide a more holistic, balanced, and reliable evaluation of alternatives. By integrating
68 diverse perspectives, EnseMCDA enhance comprehensiveness of decision-making processes,
69 enabling stakeholders to make more informed and objective decisions.

70 The aim of this research is the development and application of an EnseMCDA technique to
71 support more robust ocean planning decisions based on a national case study for the High
72 Potential Areas for Offshore Wind Energy (HPA-OWE) settled in the first Spanish Maritime
73 Spatial Plan.

74 The manuscript is structured as follows: The results section describes the 39 criteria database
75 describing the ecological, social, economic, energy-related, spatial and
76 technical/technological performance of the 19 the HPA-OWE (Fig. 1 and 2). Then we
77 describe the EnseMCDA ranking and the optimal ranking results (Fig. 3; Table 2) for each
78 HPA-OWE based on three MCDA methods (TOPSIS - Technique for Order of Preference by
79 Similarity to Ideal Solution; MMOORA - Multi-Objective Optimization by Ration Analysis
80 and VIKOR - Multicriteria Optimization and Compromise Solution)^{19–21}. The EnseMCDA
81 coupled with a non-conditioned weighting mechanism with importance weights attributed
82 uniformly through a Monte Carlo simulation to derive more robust decision. We describe the
83 emerging trade-offs in the four planning subdivisions (Fig. 4) by applying a Random Forest
84 (RM) Machine-Learning (ML) technique to identify mean square error (MSE) as criteria
85 importance indicator. The discussion section addresses the findings and outlines potential
86 future research directions.

87

88 **Study area**

89 On February 2023 the Spanish Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic
90 Challenge adapted the first Spanish Maritime Spatial Plan (*Planes de Ordenación del*
91 *Espacio Marítimo* – POEM; BOE-A-2023-5704)⁶, by the Council of Ministers by Royal
92 Decree. It establishes plans for five planning subdivisions (Fig. 1): Canary Islands (CAN);
93 Straight-Alborán (ESAL); Levantine-Balearic (LEBA), South-Atlantic (SUR) and North-
94 Atlantic (NOR). There are 19 HPA-OWE covering 0.4% (5056.7 km²) of the entire Spanish
95 EEZ (Table 1). The two HPA-OWE located in the ESAL planning subdivision have highest
96 sea space occupation 4.9% (1234 km²). At the time of release of the POEM no HPA-OWE
97 were defined in the South Atlantic (SUR) subdivision. The National Integrated Plan for
98 Energy and Climate (PNIEC) foresees to install 3 GW of offshore wind capacity by 2030.

99

100 Fig. 1. The map represents the five planning subdivisions of the Spanish Maritime Spatial
 101 Plan including 19 high potential areas for offshore wind energy (HPA-OWE) development.
 102 Source: BOE-A-2023-5704.

103
 104 Table 1. Planning subdivisions and space occupation of the HPA-OWE in square kilometres
 105 (km²) and percentage (%).

POEM Subdivisions	Nr. of HPA-OWE	Area in km ² (%)	Mean Depth (m)	HPA-OWE (km ²)	HPA-OWE space demand per subdivision (%)
Canary Islands (CAN)	6	536776 (47.6)	-3574.3	605.1	0.1
Straight y Alborán (ESAL)	2	25200.3 (2.2)	-867.1	1234	4.9
Levantine-Balearic (LEBA)	3	231547 (20.5)	-1661.1	475	0.2
North-Atlantic (NOR)	8	320221 (28.4)	-3698.4	2742.6	0.9
South-Atlantic (SUR)	0	14299.4 (1.3)	-353.4	/	/
TOTAL	19	1128043.7 (100%)		5056.7 (0.4%)	

106

107 Results

108 Criteria performance

109 Fig. 2 provides an overview of the 39 criteria and the planning tier setup. We summarize the
 110 most noticeable aspects. The *Coexistence Tier* is the overall tier ($n = 39$ criteria) that
 111 incorporates the socio-ecological tier ($n = 10$ criteria), technical/technological tier ($n = 10$
 112 criteria); spatial-efficiency tier ($n = 11$ criteria) and the energy-equity tier ($n = 8$ criteria).
 113 *Spatial-Efficiency criteria*. NOR2 is the most extended HPA-OWE development, it is the
 114 most constrained area as located in military areas and shipping lanes and has highest intensity
 115 of interactions with commercial fishery (27,997 hours of displacement in 2021). NOR3 is the
 116 area with the highest collision risk potential in the North Atlantic subdivision and ESAL1 in
 117 the Mediterranean. Eight HPA-OWE fully overlap with restricted areas (Gov_perc) for

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118 offshore wind energy development. There are three HPA-OWE that fully or partially overlap
119 with marine protected areas in the Canary Islands (CANFV1, CANFV2 and CANLANZ1),
120 the Strait-Alborán (ESAL2) and North Atlantic (NOR8). *Socio-Ecological criteria.* HPA-
121 OWE located in the North Atlantic subdivision shows higher distance from shore (28-13 km).
122 Mediterranean HPA-OWE are mostly located in high population areas such as ESAL1 and 2.
123 Highest urbanization patterns are in ESAL1 (20.5%), NOR1 (16.9%) and LEBA1 (15.3%).
124 Ecological risks to birds and fish resources are higher in Mediterranean HPA-OWE compared
125 to the North Atlantic subdivision. *Energy-Equity criteria.* Coastal provinces of LEBA1 to 3
126 have the highest GDP per capita (2021) compared to coastal provinces. Renewable energy
127 percentage is highest in NOR5 and lowest in the LEBA2 and 3 located in the Balearic
128 Islands. Unemployment rates are high in the Canary Islands and the ESAL1 and 2.
129 *Technical/Technological criteria.* Multi-use potentials (MU_Idx) with offshore wind energy
130 – aquaculture MU are NOR1 (score 1) and NOR 2-4 (score 0.52) in the North Atlantic.
131 Multi-use potentials with Photovoltaic power are highest in the Canary Island, Strait-
132 Alborán and Levantine Balearic subdivisions. Increased storm frequency due to climate
133 change can cause damage to infrastructure and to the operational safety of the site is most

134 relevant in the Mediterranean HPA-OWD (LEBA1, ESAL2 and 1).

135 Fig. 2. Performance of the 39 criteria for each of the 19 HPA-OWE development. Table 2
 136 provides the abbreviations and methodological description of each criteria.

137

138 **Ranking of HPA-OWE**

139 Results for the ranking of the HPA-OWE were presented for a data frame of 390,000 weights
 140 and 30,000 ranking results. They were graphically presented as boxplots (Fig. 3) in terms of
 141 median rank (\tilde{x}) and as interquartile range of ranks (*IQR*). We synthesize the results for each
 142 planning tier in the Atlantic (NOR and CAN) and for the Mediterranean subdivisions (LEBA
 143 and ESAL):

- 144 • *Coexistence Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivision NOR1 ($\tilde{x} = 2$; *IQR* = 1-3) and NOR4 (\tilde{x}
 145 = 2; *IQR* = 1-3) and in the Mediterranean subdivisions LEBA3 ($\tilde{x} = 8$; *IQR* = 6-10)
 146 and LEBA1 ($\tilde{x} = 8$; *IQR* = 5-11).
- 147 • *Spatial-Efficiency Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivisions NOR4 ($\tilde{x} = 1$; *IQR* = 1-2) and
 148 NOR1 ($\tilde{x} = 4$; *IQR* = 3-6) and in the Mediterranean subdivisions LEBA3 ($\tilde{x} = 6$; *IQR*

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- 149 = 3-8) and LEBA1 ($\tilde{x} = 11$; $IQR = 10-12$).
- 150 • *Energy Equity Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivision CANGC1 ($\tilde{x} = 3$; $IQR = 2-6$) and
- 151 CANTEN1 ($\tilde{x} = 4$; $IQR = 3-7$) and in the Mediterranean subdivisions ESAL1 ($\tilde{x} = 1$;
- 152 $IQR = 1-8$) and LEBA1 ($\tilde{x} = 5$; $IQR = 2-8$).
- 153 • *Socio-Ecological Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivision NOR1 ($\tilde{x} = 2$; $IQR = 1-4$) and
- 154 NOR3 ($\tilde{x} = 2$; $IQR = 1-3$) and in the Mediterranean subdivisions ESAL1 ($\tilde{x} = 17$;
- 155 $IQR = 12-19$) and ESAL2 ($\tilde{x} = 9$; $IQR = 5-13$).
- 156 • *Technical/Technological Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivision 8 HPA-OWE are within the
- 157 first 10 ranks, e.g. NOR1 ($\tilde{x} = 1$; $IQR = 1-4$) and NOR4 ($\tilde{x} = 2$; $IQR = 1-2$) and in the
- 158 Mediterranean subdivisions LEBA1 ($\tilde{x} = 9$; $IQR =$) and LEBA2 ($\tilde{x} = 10$; $IQR = 7-$
- 159 11). To notice is that ESAL1 performance is the weakest ($\tilde{x} = 18$; $IQR = 13-19$).

160 Fig. 3. Ranking results of HPA-OWE for each planning subdivision and planning tier.

161

Optimal ranking of HPA-OWE

The optimal ranking (Table 2) provides a definitive rank (R) on how often a specific HPA-OWE alternative ranks within the top-10 (n_{top-10}). In the supplementary material (Annex 1) a detailed graphical overview of optimal rankings is available. We synthesize the results for the optimal ranks for the two best ranked HPA-OWE in the Atlantic (NOR and CAN) and in the Mediterranean subdivisions (LEBA and ESAL):

- *Coexistence Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivisions NOR1 ($R = 1$; $n_{top-10} = 29,776$), NOR4 ($R = 2$; $n_{top-10} = 29,709$); and NOR7 ($R = 3$; $n_{top-10} = 27,475$) and in the Mediterranean subdivisions LEBA3 ($R = 5$; $n_{top-10} = 22,869$) and LEBA1 ($R = 7$; $n_{top-10} = 21,217$).
- *Spatial-Efficiency Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivisions NOR4 ($R = 1$; $n_{top-10} = 29,956$); CANGC1 ($R = 3$; $n_{top-10} = 29,395$) and in the Mediterranean subdivision LEBA3 ($R = 5$; $n_{top-10} = 28,252$) and LEBA1 ($R = 10$; $n_{top-10} = 12,055$).
- *Energy Equity Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivisions CANGC1 ($R = 1$; $n = 27,383$), CANTEN1 ($R = 2$; $n_{top-10} = 26,710$) and for the Mediterranean LEBA1 ($R = 4$; $n_{top-10} = 25,422$) and ESAL1 ($R = 5$; $n_{top-10} = 24,690$).
- *Socio-Ecological Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivisions (e.g. NOR4: $R = 1$; $n_{top-10} = 29,964$; NOR3: $R = 2$; $n_{top-10} = 29,939$) and in the Mediterranean subdivisions ESAL2 ($R = 8$; $n_{top-10} = 19,074$) and LEBA1 ($R = 12$; $n_{top-10} = 11,558$).
- *Technical/Technological Tier*. In the Atlantic subdivisions NOR4 ($R = 1$; $n_{top-10} = 29,109$) and in the Mediterranean subdivisions LEBA1 ($R = 9$; $n_{top-10} = 20,706$).

Table 2. Optimal ranking for HPA-OWE for each planning subdivision and planning tier.

	Subdivisions	HPA-OWE	Planning Tiers				
			Coexistence	Spatial-Efficiency	Energy Equity	Socio-Ecological	Technical/Technological
Atlantic	Canary Islands	CANTEN1	8	9	2	9	11
		CANTEN2	11	5	3	17	16
		CANLANZ1	19	17	11	14	18
		CANGC1	6	3	1	13	14
		CANFV1	17	14	7	10	17
		CANFV2	14	12	9	11	13
	North-Atlantic	NOR1	1	4	13	3	3
		NOR2	13	16	16	7	5
		NOR3	10	11	15	2	2
		NOR4	2	1	17	1	1
		NOR5	7	2	19	5	4
		NOR6	4	8	12	6	7
		NOR7	3	7	14	4	6
		NOR8	16	18	18	16	8
Mediterranean	Levantine- Balearic	LEBA1	9	10	4	12	9
		LEBA2	12	13	8	19	10
		LEBA3	5	6	10	18	12
	Straight- Alboran	ESAL1	18	15	5	15	19
		ESAL2	15	19	6	8	15

Cost-benefit analysis at planning subdivision scale

The 13 most important criteria for each planning subdivision are represented as costs and benefits in form of cumulative mean square error ($C-MSE$; Fig. 4A) and in detail as single criterion (Fig. 4B). On overall, the $C-MSE$ shows that the *Spatial Efficiency Tier* has most

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188 importance in ESAL ($C-MSE_{ESAL} = 233.51\%$) and LEBA ($C-MSE_{LEBA} = 173.75\%$). While the
 189 *Technical/Technological Tier* has more relevance in the North Atlantic ($C-MSE_{NOR} =$
 190 198.03%) and CAN ($C-MSE_{CAN} = 244.96\%$).

191 In the *Socio-Ecological Tier* ($C-MSE_{LEBA} = 162.74\%$) and the NOR ($C-MSE_{LEBA} = 165.63\%$).
 192 Tier-specific results indicate that the Energy-Equity Tier shows that recurrent costs are
 193 associated provincial contribution to the energy balance for Levantine-Balearic ($MSE_{LEBA} =$
 194 42%) and North Atlantic ($MSE_{NOR} = 41\%$) and loss of MW due to national decarbonisation
 195 policies ($MSE_{NOR} = 37\%$).

196 The *Spatial-Efficiency Tier* are related to proximity of HPA-OWE development to marine
 197 protected areas ($MSE_{LEBA} = 85\%$), space demands ($MSE_{ESAL} = 88\%$) and presence of
 198 telecommunication subcables ($MSE_{ESAL} = 74\%$) are relevant for the Straight-Alborán
 199 subdivision. In the *Socio-Ecological Tier* habitat risks ($MSE_{NOR} = 59\%$), risks to birds
 200 ($MSE_{LEBA} = 52\%$) and risk to fish ($MSE_{ESAL} = 43\%$) and mammals ($MSE_{CAN} = 28\%$). The
 201 *Technical/Technological Tier* include Storm Frequency ($MSE_{LEBA} = 47\%$), wave height
 202 ($MSE_{NOR} = 33\%$) and depth ($MSE_{CAN} = 20\%$).

203 Fig. 4. A) Cumulative-MSE ($C-MSE$) for each planning subdivision and B) specific MSE
 204 score for 13 highest costs and benefits in the 39 criteria database.

205
 206 **Discussion**

207 In addressing the fundamental challenge of transitioning towards sustainable use of marine
 208 resources and sea space utilization, our study aims to strategically re-analyze proposed HPA-

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209 OWE sites of a national maritime spatial plan through balancing ecological, social, spatial,
210 energy-related, and technical/technological characteristics. To respond to this challenge we
211 develop a 39 criteria dataset and apply an ensemble MCDA based on three algorithms
212 resulting into a database of 30,000 ranking results. The optimal prioritization of HPA-OWE
213 development (Table 2; Annex 1) based on the coexistence planning tier are:

214 Atlantic subdivisions:

215 NOR1 ($n_{top-10} = 29,776$); NOR7 ($n_{top-10} = 27,475$) and NOR4 ($n_{top-10} = 29,709$);

216 Mediterranean subdivisions:

217 LEBA3 ($n_{top-10} = 22,869$); LEBA1 ($n_{top-10} = 21,217$) and LEBA2 ($n_{top-10} = 12,217$).

218 Our method can be extended to other geographic areas and handle decision-making problems
219 of any other sectors of the Blue Economy: For instance to reach protection targets of 30% of
220 sea space by the Biodiversity Strategy 2030, the method can be used for optimal allocation of
221 new protected sites as well as for aquaculture development, ports or any other emerging
222 marine renewables technology (e.g. wave energy converters, tidal energy etc...). The
223 EnseMCDA modelling protocol is fully open source, using R-programming and a database of
224 regional, national, European and global open data repositories (see Table 4). The adaptation
225 of an ensembled MCDA technique and the use of uniformly machine-generated weights
226 through Monte Carlo simulation have several advantages compared to traditional MCDA
227 applications:

- 228 *i)* Our technique has an enhanced robustness by combining multiple individual
229 algorithms and mitigating the weaknesses of any single method^{22–25}.
- 230 *ii)* Our technique promotes a more objective and transparent method for criteria
231 weighting, relying on empirical data rather than subjective, sector-specific or
232 expert-based knowledge usually used in offshore infrastructure suitability
233 analysis^{24,26}.
- 234 *iii)* The EnseMDCA technique is more effective in exploring different planning
235 options through the generation of a large number of weight combinations.
- 236 *iv)* The technique is more adaptable to evolving environmental, economic, policy,
237 energy security, and social conditions. This adaptability is crucial for the design of
238 MSP scenarios that have to respond to transition strategies, such as the European
239 Green Deal (COM/2019/640), the EU Nature Restoration Law (2022/304 final) or
240 the Just Transition Mechanism (2021/1056).
- 241 *v)* The EnseMCDA model can make stakeholder engagement within MSP processes
242 more dynamic, by testing planning proposals and measures for different Blue
243 Economy activities and emerging new technological solutions. This dynamism
244 stems from the ability of the model to explore of how different stakeholder
245 perception and societal values influence resources use, ensuring a more responsive
246 and inclusive decision-making process.

247 In Europe, maritime spatial planners and decision-makers face challenges in implementing
248 decarbonisation policies. Our method is concrete and transparent as it enables the testing of
249 different OWE planning scenarios under different social, ecological, economic, energy-
250 related and technological marine-coastal settings. The trade-off analysis based of ML
251 technique (Fig. 4) identified the cost-benefits in different planning subdivision providing
252 novel insights for future designs of maritime spatial plans that should aim to minimize the
253 identified costs. For instance in the ESAL subdivision planning measures are required to
254 ensure spatial-efficiency of allocation of HPA-OWE, in the LEBA technological solutions are
255 required to reduce damage from increasing storm events and in the NOR, OWE-aquaculture
256 multi-use potentialities should be further explored. Overarching to every subdivisions remain
257 the ecological risks from the interaction of the infrastructure with the ecological features that
258 appear to be different in every subdivision (Fig. 4B): risks to habitats (NOR and CAN), to

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259 birds (ESAL, LEBA), to mammals (LEBA and CAN) and to fish (ESAL). Our model informs
260 planners on the ecological risks in each planning subdivision that can in future be used to
261 provide recommendations for the design of the HPA-OWE, explore nature-inclusive
262 solutions designed for specific HPA-OWE or based on precautionary principles recommend
263 no-development areas.

264 Our study incorporates a fully novel indicator set on the energy-equity highlighting that there
265 are spatial disparities in coastal provinces and that OWE allocation needs distributional
266 equity when deploying high potential areas for offshore wind energy. The indicators include
267 energy production-consumption balance, renewable energy production, provincial
268 contribution to regional energy production, decarbonization policies aimed at coal plants
269 closure or repurposing (CRiT - Coal Regions in Transition, 2017)²⁷ and social conditions,
270 including unemployment rate (in %) and GDP per capita. Between 2019-2023, in coastal
271 regions and provinces of Spain there are at least 10 coal power plants shut down totalling
272 about 7452 MW of lost energy production (Annex 2b). Our ML results (Fig. 4) show that
273 energy equity aspects are important within the multi-criteria technique: applying National
274 Statistics data (2021; Fig. 1) shows that socio-economic wealthy coastal provinces are in
275 some cases “energy privileged” areas (Fig. 1; Annex 2a and b): For instance coastal
276 provinces of the Levantine-Balearic subdivision (LEB1-Girona province and LEBA2&3-Las
277 Palmas province) have highest GDP per capita (€28,666-€28,325 per year), comparably low
278 unemployment rates (12.7%-14.9%) in respect to Canary Island (€21,344-€21,164; 23%-
279 23.5%) and Straight-Alborán (€18,861-€19,276; 20.4%-22.2%) subdivision and their coastal
280 regions are little affected by the transition towards low-carbon energy production. However
281 the Girona province in front of LEBA1 is the most energy-reliant coastal province with most
282 negative energy balance with -3921 GWh (produced vs. consumed) among the 9 coastal
283 provinces and the Principality of Asturias.

284 The proposed socio-ecological dataset is composed by 4 risk indicators (risk to habitats,
285 marine mammals, birds and fish; Fig. 2). Particularly relevant in this context is the
286 application of cross-seabasin datasets of fish, birds and mammals at scale relevant for
287 Strategic Environmental Assessment with a common methodology applicable at
288 Mediterranean (LEBA and ESAL) and Atlantic seabasin level (NOR and CAN). The results
289 indicate the need for techniques in cumulative effects assessment that can be coupled with
290 species distribution models adequate for addressing the multiple interactions of the
291 infrastructures with the ecological receptors. The ML results for the socio-ecological tier
292 indicate that the LEBA planning subdivisions with highest importance for impacts on coastal
293 tourism sector (Fig. 4): areas show to be highly dependent on coastal tourism employment
294 (between 102,680-438,976 jobs; $MSE_{LEBA} = 63\%$) and tourism pressures (161.1-404.6
295 tourist/inhabitant; $MSE_{LEBA} = 63\%$). The ecological risks are predominant for birds ($MSE_{LEBA} = 52\%$)
296 and marine mammals ($MSE_{LEBA} = 23\%$), for fish in the ESAL ($MSE_{ESAL} = 28\%$) and
297 for marine habitats in Canary Islands ($MSE_{CAN} = 42\%$).

298 Spatial efficiency in the HPA-OWE allocation shows that the ESAL1 and 2 in the Straight-
299 Alborán subdivision faces highest planning-efficiency challenges. The C - MSE (Fig. 4A) is
300 the highest among all planning subdivisions (C - $MSE_{ESAL} = 233.81\%$). ESAL1 and 2 are the
301 HPA-OWE that have highest space demand (Fig. 4; $MSE_{ESAL} = 88\%$). In the ESAL, the
302 installation of OWE also requires planning measures associated with submerged cables
303 protection and intersection in the area ($MSE_{ESAL} = 74\%$). Our model evidence that spatial
304 compatibility of HPA-OWE with MPAs is an important planning conundrum in LEBA
305 ($MSE_{LEBA} = 85\%$) and the ESAL ($MSE_{ESAL} = 14\%$) due to spatial adjacency and in CAN
306 ($MSE_{CAN} = 40\%$) due to overlay of HPA-OWE and MPA. To analyse the interaction with
307 commercial fishery activities we analyse the overlay of HPA-OWE with fishing hours in the

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308 year 2021. The highest displacement is caused within the North Atlantic Demarcation
309 ($MSE_{NOR} = 27\%$; 34,368 hours of displacement).

310 About 14.6% of the study area is covered by military areas, so that exploring wind energy
311 potentials in military areas as envisioned in the DG ENER's SYMBIOSIS Programme²⁸ can
312 promote co-location of military area with HPA-OWE and alleviate spatial competition with
313 sectors omitted from military areas. Particularly relevant is this aspect in the Southern
314 Atlantic subdivision (see Fig. 1) where presence of military areas is particularly pronounced.

315 In terms of technical/technological tiers there is an increasing interest on European level
316 (European Maritime, Fishery and Aquaculture Fund 2023) to promote multi-use as synergic
317 use of infrastructure in maritime spatial plans (e.g. Italian MSP proposal for the Tyrrhenian
318 Sea) and identify regulatory mechanisms for multi-use licensing. Our model takes into
319 consideration OWE combination with aquaculture²⁹ and hybrid energy infrastructure with
320 solar energy³⁰. Fig. 4 shows that OWE-aquaculture is one of the important
321 technical/technological solutions in the North-Atlantic ($MSE_{NOR} = 77\%$), Canary Islands
322 ($MSE_{CAN} = 73\%$) and in the Straight-Alborán ($MSE_{ESAL} = 64\%$).

323

324 Limitations

325 The cross-seabasin nature of the study (Atlantic Ocean and Mediterranean) poses substantial
326 challenges in the data collection, criteria preparation and analysis phase. Currently for Spain,
327 there are very little comprehensive studies on biodiversity distribution applicable for entire
328 Spanish maritime spatial plan. Studies are either sea-basin focused, such as for the
329 Mediterranean (Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea,
330 Mediterranean Sea and contiguous Atlantic - Accobams³¹) or some regions of the North
331 Atlantic planning subdivision Basque Country³² and OSPAR level³³. This required in our
332 study a fit-for-purpose mapping approach through the design of spatial-ecological dataset
333 required as input for the ecological risk analysis (birds, fish and mammals). A cross-seabasin
334 mapping exercise was the use of the species abundance maps from IUCN Spatial Data
335 Portal³⁴ that were scaled on a 5 km² grid³⁵. In contrast, marine habitats were represented
336 through EUNIS maps that are scalable across the European seas. Similarly, the sensitivity
337 scores of habitat types (0-5) and ecological features were derived from sensitivity look-up
338 tables from EIONET³⁶ for the Atlantic Ocean and the Mediterranean enabled to develop a
339 scalable approach to ecological risk mapping for the study area, that can be used also in other
340 European seas.

341 We applied a 5 km buffer to survey the number of marine protected areas in the surrounding
342 of each OWE sites and to address the km² of marine protected areas within 5 km distance
343 from each HPA-OWE (see Annex 2a). Buffer zones as distance-based tool can be an
344 important instrument to enforce precautionary principle, however within a wider combination
345 of spatial indicators that could be implemented, such as technical solutions, avoidance of
346 sensitive areas and of sensitive periods, pollutant-specific mitigation measures
347 (Methodological Guidance 2021/C 437/01)³⁷. We also refer to EU nature legislation
348 (Commission Notice 2020)³⁸ that expresses the need for caution on the use of buffer zones in
349 wildlife sensitivity mapping, especially when defining zero-development areas in recognition
350 of the uncertainty associated with the spatial data and knowledge.

351 Another limitation is that small scale fishery (SSF; vessel length <15 meters) data is not
352 included in our analysis, but it is a fundamental contributor to local economies in Spain^{39,40,41}
353 and globally⁴², so that data collection techniques to better take into account interactions of
354 SSF with HPA-OWE are needed in the near future. To our knowledge only the Polish
355 Maritime Spatial Plan⁴³ provides an operational integration of SSF into a national ocean plan.

356

357 Conclusions

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358 Building on this work we argue that incorporating place-based datasets can provide important
359 insights into the energy performance of the study area and offer knowledge for more balanced
360 decision of future marine energy infrastructure allocation. Maritime spatial plans need to
361 contribute to reducing spatial inequalities by balancing environmental, social, spatial, energy-
362 related and technological characteristics of a territory. This means that planning approaches
363 aimed at locating offshore wind energy infrastructure in degraded sea areas or urbanized
364 coasts without taking into consideration the social conditions can increase spatial inequalities
365 and further impair environmental resources. Particularly important in this case are social
366 conditions in coastal territories with low income, territories affected by decarbonisation
367 policies or high unemployment.

368 Moreover knowledge on place-based socio-economic conditions is fundamental for next
369 generation maritime spatial plans and for a just energy transition. A better understanding of
370 the marine ecosystem services⁴⁴ requires the integration of Blue Economy datasets^{45,46}
371 (sectorial jobs, revenue), as they enable to understand the costs and benefits of interactions of
372 offshore wind energy with other sectors (especially commercial fishery, tourism and
373 shipping) of the Blue economy and can help to produce more informed planning outcomes
374 for society.

375 Through the five planning tiers, we explore stereotypical dimensions of planning choices and
376 the essential need for interdisciplinary knowledge and data sources for their implementation.
377 Our method provides a relevant starting point for the definition of new generation of MCDA
378 methods for more transparent and robust exploration of planning decisions in offshore wind
379 energy development that however can be extended to any other offshore infrastructure, to
380 conservation planning or any other coastal and maritime activities allocation.

381

382 Materials and methods

383 Fig. 5 lays out the methodological framework adopted in this study. In the following
384 materials and method section and in the supplementary materials a detailed description of
385 each methodological step and data sources is provided.

386

387 Fig. 5. The implementation of the study included the development of a database of 39 criteria
388 and their preparation for analysis. The Ensemble Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
389 (EnseMCDA) approach incorporates three distinct multi-criteria methodologies: TOPSIS,
390 MMOORA, and VIKOR. Each of these techniques was executed using a set of 10,000 unique
391 weights for each criterion (39 criteria x 10,000 weights = 390,000 weights). These weights
392 were derived through a Monte Carlo simulation process. Consequently, a total of 30,000
393 rankings were generated, with each methodology contributing 10,000 ranks. These rankings
394 were then consolidated and presented in the form of priority ranks and optimal priority
395 rankings. This comprehensive approach ensures a robust and reliable decision-making
396 process. Machine Learning Technique based on Random Forest was applied for the

397 identification of trade-offs using a C-MSE – cumulative means standard error (Fig. 3A) and
 398 the MSE for single criteria (Fig. 3B).

399

400 Defining Planning Tiers

401 In order to formulate planning relevant outcomes we define five exploratory planning tiers.
 402 Planning tiers can provide a set of plausible spatial planning rationales applicable to sectorial
 403 MSP challenges such as OWE development^{15,48}. Each of the five planning tiers consists of a
 404 descriptive planning narrative (Table 3) derived from the MSP Directive (2014/89/EU), the
 405 national plan (BOE-A-2023-5704) and planning research theory. In the EnseMCDA model
 406 each tier gets unpacked by a group of criteria. To note is that the co-existence tier is the
 407 overall tier and incorporates all 39 criteria displayed in Fig. 2 and described in Table 4.

408

409 Table 3. Planning tiers applied to EnseMCDA.

Planning Tiers	Description
<i>Co-existence</i> ⁶	Allocation of HPA-OWE follow <i>recital 8</i> of the EU MSP Directive (2014/89/EU) ⁴⁹ and the methodological approach of the Spanish Maritime Spatial Plan (Section 2.1.1b) ⁶ by promoting co-existence among different uses of the sea.
<i>Socio-Ecological</i> ⁵⁰	HPA-OWE should be allocated in areas where ecological and social costs are minimized this includes distant from coast to avoid visual impacts and in sea areas where cumulative risks to habitats, birds, marine mammals and fish are minimized.
<i>Spatial-Efficiency</i> ⁴⁹	HPA-OWE should be developed in areas where interactions and conflicts (<i>recital 19</i> ; 2014/89/EU) ⁴⁹ with other uses of the sea are minimized: nature protection, commercial fishery, shipping, cabling, military areas and coastal tourism.
<i>Energy Equity</i> ^{51,52}	Allocation of HPA-OWE follow a distributional equity by considering fair distribution of benefits and burdens to coastal communities, taking into account economic and social disadvantaged coastal regions/provinces, just transition towards low-carbon energy systems and sharing of burden with energetically “ <i>privileged</i> ” provinces.
<i>Technical/ Technological</i> ^{29,53}	HPA-OWE should be allocated in sea areas where technical/technological feasibility is maximized, where potentials for multi-use combinations with OWE infrastructure are maximized (with aquaculture and solar energy), weather conditions do not harm infrastructure and where capacity of energy production can be maximized.

410

411 Criteria database and preparation

412 The criteria were developed using a comprehensive open source database of indicators. In
 413 total 39 indicators were developed and organized into four categories (ecological, social,
 414 spatial/technical and energy equity; see Annex 2a). Table 4 provides an overview of the
 415 criteria including the cost or benefit attribution ($n = 29$ are costs and $n = 10$ are benefits), a
 416 methodological description and the data sources. The preparation of the spatial layers was
 417 based in ArcGIS 10.7 (ESRI, 2022). The 19 HPA-OWE (high potential areas for offshore
 418 wind energy areas - “*Zonas de alto potencial para el desarrollo de la energía eólica
 419 marina*”) and the 5 planning subdivisions of the Spanish Maritime Spatial Plan (“*Ámbito
 420 espacial del POEM*”) were downloaded from MITECO, 2023 (see Fig. 1).

421 The indicators were then categorized based on a literature review⁵⁴ into costs and benefits.
 422 We apply a precautionary principle in the cost and benefit attribution selection, so that in case
 423 a criterion is used in ambiguous way in different literature, it is defined as cost in our model.
 424 Costs refer to anti-ideal solutions that reflect the worst possible value for a specific indicator
 425 (e.g. *collision risk*, *distance to coast*, *overlay with protected areas*). Benefits refer to ideal
 426 solutions that reflect the best possible value for a specific indicator (e.g. *average wind speed*,
 427 *distance from ports*).

428

429 Table 4. Overview, description and unit of the integrated geospatial database development for
 430 the analysis of decision dimensions. *Note*: C-Cost, B-Benefit.

#	Criteria (C)	Abbr	C/B	Methodological description
Spatial-Efficiency				
C_1	<i>Area</i>	<i>Area_sqkm</i>	B	[km^2]. Area occupied by HPA-OWE. Source: https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cartografia-y-sig/ide/descargas/costas-medio-marino/poem.html

C ₂	Constrained zones ^{15,16,55}	Constrain _n	C	[Number of constrained areas inside the OWE site]. Shipping lanes, MPAs and military areas are considered as “constrained areas” where any other activity is excluded. The value can range from 0 (no constrain) to 3 (high constrain). Source: https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/ ; https://www.protectedplanet.net/en .
C ₃	Collision Risk ^{55,56}	CR _{Ix}	C	[Mean Vessel Density within 6482 m safety buffer from the OWE perimeter]. The maximum safety buffer identified in literature for OWE sites. Vessel density is considered for Tankers, Cargo, Passenger and Sailing vessels. If it is between 0.5nm – 3.5nm (926m – 6482m) this is deemed tolerable if the risk is being reduced to as low as reasonably practicable; The Route Density Maps are produced and provided to EMODnet by the European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA) solely for the purposes of EMODnet. EMODnet shall ensure the storage of the received the data and prepare and distribute maps via the EMODnet portal using its own data conversion and presentation tools and methodologies. The data made available through EMODnet portal and the maps produced by EMODnet from the data shall have reference to EMSA as the source of data. Users shall make reference to EMSA as the source of data when using them, promoting them or generating related publications, whatever the purpose. EMODnet Human Activities accepts no responsibility or liability whatsoever for the re-use of content accessible on its website. Source: https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/ .
C ₄	Restricted vs prohibited sites	Gov _{perc}	C	[%]. This criterion describes if the HPA-OWE site is fully or partially located inside a restricted area. Source: https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cartografia-y-sig/ide/descargas/costas-medio-marino/poem.html .
C ₅	Fishery Displacement ⁵⁷	Mean_Fish_effort_hours	C	[Sum of hours in fishing effort (FE) foregone within the perimeter of the OWE site]. The Displacement for the years 2022-2023 is calculated using the Spatial Statistics as Table toolbox available in ArcGIS 10.7. The higher FE, the higher the number of fishing hours inside the HPA-OWE site and therefore the displacement score: $FE = R_{OWE} \cap F_{GFW}$ Source: https://globalfishingwatch.org/map/index
C ₆	Overlay of MPAs	MP _{perc}	C	[Number of protected areas within 5 km buffer]. MPA usually include already a protection buffer, however it is unclear whether in this case if they include. We use safety buffer to enhance the precautionary approach in this study. Source: https://www.protectedplanet.net/en .
C ₇	Adjacency to MPA	MPA_5km_buffer	C	[%]. Percentage of protected areas within 5 km buffer from the HPA PWE perimeter. Source: https://www.protectedplanet.net/en .
C ₈	Distance from MPAs	MPA_5km_buffer_n	C	[Number of protected areas within 5 km buffer]. MPA usually include already a protection buffer, however it is unclear whether in this case if they include. We use safety buffer to enhance the precautionary approach in this study. Source: https://www.protectedplanet.net/en .
C ₉	Space demand	Space_dem_perc	C	[%]. Percentage of area occupied by HPA-OWE inside the respective planning subdivision. Source: https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/cartografia-y-sig/ide/descargas/costas-medio-marino/poem.html (HPA-OWE);
C ₁₀	Distance to electricity substation	Substation_dist_km	C	[km]. Calculated from the centre point of OWE polygon to the closest substations, according to national electricity map (<i>mapa red electrica, 2016</i>). Source: https://eepublicdownloads.entsoe.eu/clean-documents/Publications/maps/2019/Map_ENTSO-E-4.000.000.pdf .
C ₁₁	Telecommunication cables ⁵⁵	Telecom_km	C	[km] Length of telecommunication cables inside the HPA-OWE sites. Source: https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/
Energy-Equity				
C ₁₂	Decarbonization policies	Decarbonization_lostMW	C	[Index]. Lost MegaWatt (MW) production due to closure of coal plain coastal regions in front of HPA-OWE sites in the period 2019-2023. The index is normalized on a scale from 0 to 1. See Annex 2a for further details on decommissioned power plants. Source: https://www.boe.es/buscar/act.php?id=BOE-A-2020-6621&p=20230629&tm=1#an .
C ₁₃	Energy Balance ⁵⁸	Energy_bal_Idx	C	[Index]. Net provincial energy generation and provincial energy consumed ($E_{generation} - E_{production}$). Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm
C ₁₄	GDP per capita ⁵⁸	GDPpercapita	C	[€/inhabitant]. Annual GDP per inhabitant in a given coastal province. Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm .
C ₁₅	Installation_Capacity ⁵⁹	Install_Cap_MW	B	[MW/km ²]. The technical potential for each opportunity zone is retrieved from the Energy System Management Assistance Program (ESMAP) for Spain. It has been computed by assuming a density of 3 MW per km ² for wind speeds between 7–8 m/s and 4 MW per km ² for wind speeds greater than 8 m/s. Source: https://www.esmap.org/esmap_offshorewind_techpotential_analysis_maps

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C ₁₆	Population Density	Pop_dens_pper_sqkm	C	[inhabitant/km ²]. Population density per coastal province in front of HPA-OWE sites for 2021. Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm .
C ₁₇	Contribution to regional renewable energy production ⁵⁸	Re_energy_perc	B	[%]. Provincial production of energy from renewable resources (hydropower, wind, nuclear, solar) for the year 2019. Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm .
C ₁₈	Contribution to regional energy production ⁵⁸	Reg_contr_perc	B	[%]. Contribution of the province to regional energy production in 2019, including combustibles, solar energy (photovoltaic and thermic), wind energy and nuclear. Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm .
C ₁₉	Unemployment ⁵⁸	Unemployment_perc	C	[%]. Percentage of unemployment for the year 2021. Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm .
Socio-Ecological				
C ₂₀	Coastal tourism	Beaches_n	C	[number of beaches]. Coastal tourism was taken into consideration by defining the number of beach within a buffer area of 82 km from the OWE site. 82 km is considered the visibility limit of a turbine of 250 m height. Dataset on beaches was collected from GeoFabrik 2022. Source: https://www.geofabrik.de/ .
C ₂₁	Distance from shore	Distance_km	B	[km]. Shortest distance from shore to OWE site. This was mapped with ArcGIS. Source: https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/ .
C ₂₂	Population density	Pop_n	C	[Population/km ²]. Density of population in coastal provinces for the year 2017. Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm
C ₂₃	Ecological risks - Birds	RiskBirds_Idx	C	[Index]. Ecological risk ^{25,40,41} assessment was performed as the product of the Sensitivity S of the i -th ecological feature (marine mammals, fish species, birds and habitats), that are exposed Exp to the j -th stressor exerted by an OWE installation: $R_{HPA-OWE} = S_i \times Exp_j$ whereas, $Exp_j = E f_j \times d_j$ $E f_j$ = number of ecological features in terms of species (marine mammals, fish species, birds) or number of different habitats (Circalittoral sand, Infralittoral rock and biogenic reef, Infralittoral sand, Offshore circalittoral coarse sediment, Offshore circalittoral mixed sediment, Offshore circalittoral mud, Offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef, Offshore circalittoral sand, Bathyal). d_j = propagation distance of pressure j in km (0 to maximum 50 km). The exposure (Exp) includes the following stressors according to the sea-basin wide harmonized pressure and sensitivity score available in Annex 2c and d of the European Information Network (EIONET) Technical Report: i) Introductions of non indigenous species; ii) Physical loss of seabed; iii) Physical disturbance to seabed; iv) Changes to hydrological conditions; v) Input of hazardous substances; vi) Input of continuous anthropogenic sound. Source: https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/ (marine habitats); https://www.iucnredlist.org/resources/spatial-data-download (marine mammals, fish and birds)
C ₂₄	Ecological risks - Fish	Riskfish_Idx	C	
C ₂₅	Ecological risks - Habitats	RiskHabitats_Id x	C	
C ₂₆	Ecological risks - Marine Mammals	Riskmammals_I dx	C	
C ₂₇	Employment in tourism sector ⁵⁸	Tourist_employment	C	
C ₂₈	Tourism pressure	Tourist_press_t ouristper1kinh	C	[number of arrivals per 1000 inhabitants]. Tourism pressure: number of arrivals per 1000 inhabitants in coastal province for the year 2021. Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm .
C ₂₉	Urbanization	Urbanization_perc	B	[%]. Percentage of urbanized coastal municipalities within 50 km from the HPA-OWE based on CORINE Land Cover 2018. The land uses include: airports, construction sites, continuous urban fabric, discontinuous urban fabric, dump sites, industrial or commercial units, mineral extraction sites, port areas, road and rail networks and associated land and sport and leisure facilities. Source: https://doi.org/10.2909/960998c1-1870-4e82-8051-6485205ebbac (raster 100 m)
Technical/Technological				
C ₃₀	Average wind speed ⁶²	AWS_mpersec	B	[m/s]. Average wind speed at 200 meter height derived from the Global Wind Atlas (2021), calculated with ArcGIS 10.7 zonal Statistics. Source: https://globalwindatlas.info/en
C ₃₁	Depth ⁵⁵	Depth_m	C	[m]. Average depth of the OWE site polygon calculated using EMODNet (2020) Bathymetry with ArcGIS 10.7 zonal Statistics. Source: https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/ .
C ₃₂	Wave height	MeanWaveHeight_m	C	[meters]. The mean wave height inside a HPA-OWE was calculated with ArcGIS 10.7 zonal statistics using Iberia Biscay Ireland Significant Wave Height extreme from Reanalysis of the Copernicus Marine Services. Source: https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/IBI_OMI_SEASTATE_extreme_var_

				swh_mean_and_anomaly/description
<i>C</i> ₃₃	<i>Ocean Multi-Use</i> ^{11,55,63}	<i>MU_Idx</i>	B	<p>[<i>Index</i>]. This index describes the MU potential for each OWE site in relation with the aquaculture sector. The index reflects the industrial agglomeration, which is a form of spatial organization in which the same industry or related enterprises are relatively concentrated within a specific geographical scope⁶⁴. Level of commercial specialization of the coastal province to aquaculture development was defined by the number of companies active in the finfish, mussel and algae sector (<i>C_{aquaculture}</i>). The level of specialization of coastal regions to the OWE sector was calculated by the number of companies in OWE in Spain (<i>C_{owe}</i>) using information derived from JRC's Low Carbon Observatory Report (2019)⁶⁵. Distance (<i>d_{ports}</i>; in km) from the centre point of the OWE infrastructure from major regional industrial ports in Spain according to Filgueira-Vizoso, et al. (2021)⁶⁵ using distance toolbox in ArcGIS.</p> $MU_{potential} = (C_{aquaculture} + C_{owe}) d_{ports}$ <p>Source: https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/</p>
<i>C</i> ₃₄	<i>Photo Voltaic potential</i> ⁶	<i>OWEPV_Watt</i>	B	<p>[<i>Watt/m²</i>]. Photovoltaic Resource calculated for June, July, and August of 2022. Data used to calculate PV resource: 1. ERA5 10m Wind Speed (m/s); 2. ERA5 2m Air Temperature (K); 3. Meteosat Surface Solar Irradiance (Watt/m²)³⁰</p> <p>Source: https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview; https://osi-saf.eumetsat.int/products/osi-304-a.</p>
<i>C</i> ₃₅	<i>Distance to ports</i>	<i>Port_dist_km</i>	C	<p>[<i>km</i>]. Shortest distance from shore to HPA-OWE site calculated with distance tool of ArcGIS 10.7</p> <p>Source: https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/.</p>
<i>C</i> ₃₆	<i>Slope suitability</i>	<i>Slope_suit</i>	C	<p>[<i>%</i>]. Percentage of highly suitable slope (0-4 degrees) for floating offshore wind energy infrastructure within the HPA-OWE sites. Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm.</p>
<i>C</i> ₃₇	<i>Thunderstorms</i> ⁶⁶	<i>Storms_Idx</i>	C	<p>[<i>frequency of thunderstorms</i>]. This indicator defines the number of Thunderstorms within the period from 2021-2050 based on 14 regional climate models (EURO-CORDEX). The datasets is made available through Rädler et al. 2019. The dataset is aggregated as wind, lightning and hail.</p> $S_{2021-2050} = f_{wind} + f_{lighting} + f_{hail}$ <p>Source: Rädler et al. 2019⁶⁶</p>
<i>C</i> ₃₈	<i>Substrate suitability</i>	<i>Substrate_suit_perc</i>	C	<p>[<i>%</i>]. Percentage of highly suitable substrate (sand, fine mud, sandy mud, muddy sand) for floating offshore wind energy infrastructure within the HPA-OWE sites. Source: https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/listaoperaciones.htm.</p>
<i>C</i> ₃₉	<i>Technical Potential</i> ⁵⁹	<i>TP_x</i>	B	<p>[<i>Index</i>]. Total installation capacity estimated by the technical capacity calculated using Wind Atlas datasets and ESMAP (Energy Sector Management Assistance Programme). The technical potential for each HPA-OWE site is computed assuming a density of 3 MW per km² for wind speeds between 7–8 m/s and 4 MW per km² for wind speeds greater than 8 m/s. The indicator is normalized from 1 (high potential opportunity area) to 0 (low potential opportunity area) defines the overlay with the opportunity area. Source: https://www.esmap.org/esmap_offshorewind_techpotential_analysis_maps</p>

431

432 Creating a Decision matrix

433 After the development of the indicator database a decision matrix (Table 5) is set up with
 434 *HPA-OWE*₁₋₁₉ being the 19 alternative HPA-OWE development defined within the Spanish
 435 Maritime Spatial plan. The alternatives are characterized by a total of 39 criteria (*C*₁ to *C*₃₉)
 436 described in Table 4.

437

438 Table 5. EnseMCDA decision matrix.

HPA-OWE Alternatives	<i>C</i> ₁	<i>C</i> ₂	...	<i>C</i> ₃₉
<i>HPA-OWE</i> ₁	<i>x</i> ₁₁	<i>x</i> ₁₂	...	<i>x</i> _{1n}
<i>HPA-OWE</i> ₂	<i>x</i> ₂₁	<i>x</i> ₂₂	...	<i>x</i> _{2n}
...	<i>x</i> _{ij}	...
<i>HPA-OWE</i> ₁₉	<i>x</i> _{m1}	<i>x</i> _{m2}	...	<i>x</i> _{mn}

439

440 Ensembled Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis

441 We apply an ensembled Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (*EnseMCDA*) technique based on
 442 the “MCDM” (Multi-Criteria Decision Modelling) library available in R programming
 443 language⁶⁷. The library has the advantage that it can rank alternatives using three MCDM

444 techniques as follows (Table 6): i) TOPSIS (*Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity*
 445 *to Ideal Solution*)¹⁹; ii) Multi-MOORA (*Multi-Objective Optimization by Ration Analysis*
 446 *(MOORA) - Full Multiplicative Form*)²¹; iii) VIKOR (*Multicriteria Optimization and*
 447 *Compromise Solution*)²⁰. Once the cost or benefit of the criteria used and their relative weight
 448 have been defined, the algorithms will assign a score for each alternative. However, although
 449 it is objective to decide whether the criterion represents a cost or a benefit, the weight
 450 attributed to each criterion varies based on the opinions of experts. In order to overcome the
 451 expert-based weighting we apply a non-conditioned weighting mechanism with weights
 452 attributed via Monte Carlo simulation, using a continuous uniform distribution. Namely,
 453 10,000 uniformly distributed weights were generated for each criterion, in a range between
 454 0.1 (low importance) and 0.99 (very important), as shown in Table 6. The uniform
 455 distribution represents an optimal choice in the Monte Carlo simulation when a certain
 456 variable is contained in a certain interval, but there is no reason to consider some values more
 457 plausible than others⁶⁸. In this way, the alternatives will be evaluated for a wide range of
 458 weights and compared to the traditional method there are two main advantages: i) The most
 459 robust alternatives can be highlighted, whose score varies little as the weights vary; ii) The
 460 criteria that most influence the score of the alternatives can be recognized. The adopted
 461 approach generates 10,000 rankings for each MCDA method. These results in a total of
 462 30,000 rankings, corresponding to the number of weights produced through the Monte Carlo
 463 simulation. The results were visually represented using boxplots (Fig. 3) to display all the
 464 scores acquired from each HPA-OWE.

466 Table 6. Normalization methods and three EnseMCDA were applied. All algorithms were
 467 retrieved from R MCDM Package documentation⁶⁷.

MCDM Methods	Algorithm
Normalization	TOPSIS and MMOORA normalization of the x_{ij} values: $n_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^m (x_{ij})^2}}$ VIKOR normalization of the x_{ij} values: $n_{ij} = \frac{f_j^* - x_{ij}}{f_j^* - f_j^-}$
TOPSIS - <i>Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution</i> ¹⁹	Calculate the ideal or reference solutions, which are the Positive Ideal Solution (PIS), A^+ , and the Negative Ideal Solution (NIS), A^- , as follows: $(PIS) = A^+ - \{v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_j^+\}$ $(NIS) = A^- - \{v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_j^-\}$ <p>where $v_j^+ = \max_i(v_{ij})$ and $v_j^- = \min_i(v_{ij})$ if the j^{th} criterion is benefit; and $v_j^+ = \min_i(v_{ij})$ and $v_j^- = \max_i(v_{ij})$ if the j^{th} criterion is cost, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.</p> <p>Calculate the distances from every alternative to the ideal solution, being d_i^+ the distance to A^+ and d_i^- the distance to A^-.</p> <p>Best</p> $d_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^+)^2}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n,$ <p>Worst</p> $d_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (v_{ij} - v_j^-)^2}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m; j = 1, 2, \dots, n,$ <p>which corresponds to the m-dimensional Euclidean distance.</p> <p>Calculate the relative Closeness:</p> $R_i = \frac{d_i^-}{d_i^+ + d_i^-}$
MMOORA - <i>Multi-Objective Optimization by Ration Analysis</i> ²¹	$u(y, z) = k_y u_y(y) + k_z u_z(z) + k_{yz} u_y(y) u_z(z)$ <p>If $k_{yz} = 0$ we return to the additive form. For Keeney the additive form is rather a limiting case of the multiplicative utility function (Keeney 1973: 110)¹. If $k_{yz} \neq 0$, then the utility function possesses a multiplicative part: if $k_{yz} > 0$, then the mutual influence is positive,</p>

if $k_{yz} < 0$, then the mutual influence has a negative effect on the utility function.

$$U_j = \prod_{i=1}^n X_{ij}$$

VIKOR -
Multicriteria
Optimization and
Compromise Solution
(in Serbian
VišeKriterijumska
Optimizacija I
Kompromisno
Resenje)²⁰

Determine the best f_j^* and worst f_j^- values of each criterion as $f_j^* = \max_i(x_{ij})$ and $f_j^- = \min_i(x_{ij})$ if the j^{th} criterion is benefit, and as $f_j^* = \min_i(x_{ij})$ and $f_j^- = \max_i(x_{ij})$ if the j^{th} criterion is cost, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ $y j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

Calculate value S_i and R_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$:

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j * n_{ij}$$

$$R_i = \max[w_j * n_{ij}]$$

$$Q_i = v + \frac{(S_i - S^*)}{S^- + S^*} + (1 - v) \frac{(R_i - R^*)}{R^- + R^*}$$

where $S^* = \min_i(S_i)$, $S^- = \max_i(S_i)$, $R^* = \min_i(R_i)$, $R^- = \max_i(R_i)$, and $v \in [0, 1]$.

Parameter v balances the relative importance of indexes S and R .

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Table 6. Summary of uniformly distributed weights matrix, defined for the 39 criteria (C_1 to C_{39}).

Weights	C_1	C_2	C_3	...	C_{39}	$\sum W_i$
W_1	0.12	0.08	0.53	W_{C_i}	0.24	1
W_2	0.51	...	0.21	1
W_3	...	0.32	1
...	0.02	...	0.03	...	0.89	1
W_{10000}	...	0.21	0.09	1

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Optimal ranking

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Reducing complexity in spatial decision making is pivotal as it helps building consensus and agreement among stakeholders with diverse backgrounds and perspectives. For this purpose we synthesize results with an optimal ranking. The optimal ranking is the definitive rank (R) that calculates how often a HPA-OWE falls within the top-10 ranks (n_{top-10}) of the ranking database generated. Table 2 provides a synthesis of the results for the Atlantic (CAN and NOR) and the Mediterranean subdivisions (ESAL and LEBA). In Annex 1 a graphical representation of n_{top-10} is provided.

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Trade-off analysis

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Trade-off analysis is the process of evaluating the costs (disadvantages) and benefits (advantages) associated with different decisions, actions, or allocations of resources within maritime areas. In ocean planning, trade-off analysis is important, because it helps choosing optimal location of wind farms and minimizes conflicts among the multiple sectors, resources and values. This improves transparency in the decision-making process, promotes efficient solutions and maximizes sector values. In ocean planning, a limitation of trade-off analysis is the local geographic scope and its dual or triple sector analysis (e.g. offshore wind energy – fishery – marine protection)^{69,70} often settled into the ecosystem services domain⁵⁴.

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To identify the costs and benefits that significantly impact the scores of the 19 HPA-OWE alternatives examined in this study, we employed the random forest machine learning (ML) algorithm from the “*randomForest*” R package⁷¹. This algorithm is suitable for both classification and regression tasks and assesses the importance of variables involved in the model by calculating the increase in the model’s mean square error (MSE) when a variable is omitted. The algorithm was trained using the weight matrix, which was assigned to the 39 criteria, as predictors (e.g. $W_1, W_2, \dots, W_{10000}$) and the average score derived from the EnsemCDA for a specific HPA-OWE alternative (e.g. \tilde{x} Scores- W_1, \tilde{x} Scores- W_2, \dots, \tilde{x} Scores- $W_{10,000}$) as response variable. This training process enabled the algorithm to discern how score variations for each HPA-OWE are influenced by the weights assigned to the

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500 different criteria. To characterize the importance of the planning tiers at planning subdivision
501 level we formulate a cumulative MSE (*C-MSE*) for each planning subdivision. The results
502 (Fig. 4B) unveil what costs and benefits affect most significantly the average score obtained
503 from the four planning subdivisions, providing a robust trade-off analysis at planning scale.
504 Annex 3 of the supplementary material provides a look-up table with the MSE scores for
505 each planning subdivision and planning tier.

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507 **Data availability**

508 The dataset composing the criteria used in this study are available in the supplementary
509 material and upon request to the corresponding author for reasonable use in research.

510

511 **Acknowledgement**

512 This research was funded by *Blue-Paths – Addressing Sustainability Transition Pathways in*
513 *the Blue Economy* (<https://blue-paths.eu/>) funded by the European Commission (Grant
514 Agreement: 101062188) under the HORIZON – Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions 2021 of
515 the Horizon Europe program.

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517 **Supplementary Material**

518 **Annex 1.** Overview of optimal ranks according to five planning tiers and the 19 HPA-OWE
 519 development. For instance NOR1 ranks in the top-10 for the coexistence tier about $n = 29,776$
 520 times, NOR4 $n = 29,964$ in the socio-ecological tier, and so on.

521 **Annex 2a.** 39 criteria according to five planning tiers. The sum of tiers refers to co-existence
 522 tier, that corresponds to the overall scenario.
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1.Spatial-Efficiency Tier										
HPA-OWE	Area_sqkm	Space_dem_perc	Constrain_n	CR_Ix	MP_perc	Gov_perc	mean_Fish_effort_hours	Telecom_km	MPA_5km_buffer_%	MPA_5km_buffer_n
CANFV1	205.68	0.04	1	0.04	100	100	1.12	0	98.99	1
CANFV2	17.38	0	1	0.05	100	0	1	0	97.87	1
CANGC1	177.62	0.03	1	0.09	0	0	5.98	0	0	0
CANLANZ1	103.71	0.02	1	0.06	94	100	1.68	0	75.57	3
CANTEN1	23.36	0	0	0.04	0	55	12.24	0	10.79	2
CANTEN2	77.39	0.02	0	0.02	0	64	7.7	0	0	0
ESAL1	540.31	1.98	1	0.23	0	100	6.17	114.7	0	0
ESAL2	693.64	2.54	1	0.1	16	100	385.56	62.2	22.19	1
LEBA1	249.99	0.11	0	0.09	0	100	644.12	0	41.97	3
LEBA2	147.36	0.06	0	0.05	0	100	108.38	0	29.19	4
LEBA3	77.66	0.03	0	0.03	0	100	162.02	0	0	0
NOR1	120.65	0.04	1	0.11	0	0	1043.75	0	0	0
NOR2	1845.51	0.58	2	0.09	0	0	27996.7	15.6	0	0
NOR3	115.12	0.04	1	1	0	0	1118.6	0	0	0
NOR4	79.14	0.03	0	0.09	0	0	907.96	0	0	0
NOR5	240.18	0.08	1	0.13	0	0	1004.57	0	5.34	1
NOR6	106.54	0.03	0	0.11	0	100	437.85	0	0	0
NOR7	81.31	0.03	1	0.1	0	0	528.66	0	33.97	1
NOR8	154.1	0.05	2	0.13	81	100	1329.44		61.32	2

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2.Energy Equity Tier								
HPA-OWE	GDPpercapita	Unemployment_perc	Decarbonization_lostM W	Re_energy_perc	Energy_bal_Idx	Reg_contr_perc	Pop_dens_ppersqkm	Install_Cap_MW
CANFV1	21164	23	1	8	0.66	84.88	264	4
CANFV2	21164	23	1	8	0.66	84.88	264	4
CANGC1	21344	23.5	1	50	0.16	15.12	289	4
CANLANZ1	21164	23	1	8	0.66	84.88	264	4
CANTEN1	21344	23.5	1	50	0.16	15.12	289	4
CANTEN2	21344	23.5	1	50	0.16	15.12	289	4
ESAL1	19276	20.4	0.54	42	0.14	10.07	228	3
ESAL2	18861	22.2	0.54	44	0.29	6.89	72	4
LEBA1	28666	12.7	1	38	0	1.56	130	4
LEBA2	28325	14.9	0.94	3	0.29	100	227	3
LEBA3	28325	14.9	0.94	3	0.29	100	227	3
NOR1	22973	13.9	1	86	0.22	7.71	208	4
NOR2	24714	10.6	0.35	32	1	51.29	139	4
NOR3	24714	10.6	0.35	32	1	51.29	139	4
NOR4	24714	10.6	0.35	32	1	51.29	139	4
NOR5	23615	9.1	1	98	0.4	20.25	33	4
NOR6	23245	12.5	0	28	0.63	100	95	4
NOR7	23245	12.5	0	28	0.63	100	95	4
NOR8	23245	12.5	0	28	0.63	100	95	3

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3.Technical/Technological Tier										
HPA-OWE	Depth_m	AWS_mpersec	TP_x	MU_Idx	Substrate_suit_perc	Slope_suit_%	Storms_Idx	MeanWaveHeight_m	OWEPV_Watt	Port_dist_km
CANFV1	668.54	9.18	0.02	0.02	0	56.76	0.42	2.34	947.57	35.6
CANFV2	931.05	8.5	0.01	0.02	0	99.95	0.42	2.34	940.02	9.2
CANGC1	544.38	10.32	0.03	0	0	83.35	0.33	3	957.42	36.7
CANLANZ1	797.46	9.17	0.01	0	0	35.66	0.42	2.68	873.82	11.3
CANTEN1	549.59	10.84	0.01	0.12	0	7.47	0.33	1.93	919.77	18
CANTEN2	822.98	9.64	0.01	0.14	0	46.86	0.33	1.58	952.65	35
ESAL1	788.25	7.3	0.19	0	90.95	99.88	1.18	2.4	930.97	55.6
ESAL2	757.78	8.05	0.19	0	100	100	1.41	2.33	936.25	28.8
LEBA1	194.68	10.96	0.26	0.03	93.22	99.99	1.6	3.16	890.48	26.95
LEBA2	431.54	7.62	0.10	0.11	100	69.92	0.96	4.44	896.3	19.3
LEBA3	539.81	7.53	0.10	0.09	100	82.26	0.96	4.46	899.47	22.6
NOR1	132.09	8.64	1.00	1	52.65	99.65	0.53	5.98	828.48	56.5
NOR2	460	10.18	1.00	0.52	91.51	99.24	0.53	6.75	757.04	60.3
NOR3	229.49	9.98	1.00	0.52	92.73	100	0.54	6.63	741.18	32
NOR4	184.81	9.7	1.00	0.52	93.38	100	0.54	6.54	734.02	30.7
NOR5	140.13	8.78	1.00	0.04	86.36	100	0.7	5.92	703.24	30.1
NOR6	132.21	8.58	1.00	0.13	52.09	100	0.83	5.8	704.4	42.9
NOR7	144.4	8.45	1.00	0.15	72.45	99.89	0.83	5.92	702.7	49.4
NOR8	157.22	7.43	0.22	0.19	99.9	99.72	0.98	5.75	695.99	27.6

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4.Socio-ecological Tier								
HPA-OWE	Riskfish_Idx	Riskmammals_Idx	RiskBirds_Idx	RiskHabitats_Idx	Pop_n	Urbanization_perc	Beaches_n	Distance_km
CANFV1	1683	229.6	838.88	36.5	15101	6.6	142	5.42
CANFV2	1683	229.6	838.88	7.25	72594	6.6	153	5.48
CANGC1	1683	229.6	878.08	36.5	846216	6.6	120	5.8
CANLANZ1	1694	229.6	823.2	36.5	174213	6.6	138	1.71
CANTEN1	1683	221.4	909.44	107.25	5104	5	190	1.78
CANTEN2	1683	221.4	909.44	7.25	904437	5	221	1.81
ESAL1	3757.5	208.89	4735.5	6.75	1688867	20.5	157	13.57
ESAL2	3735	147.45	4120.5	6.75	485363	5.54	116	7.07
LEBA1	3375	147.45	4469	84.75	533142	15.3	289	10.69
LEBA2	3150	147.45	2849.5	98.63	91918	5.6	127	4.55
LEBA3	3127.5	147.45	2849.5	85.88	64673	5.6	114	10.63
NOR1	1628	221.4	1356.32	94.5	504990	16.9	163	22.39
NOR2	1518	213.2	1348.48	78.75	453544	5.4	334	28.38
NOR3	1474	213.2	1340.64	87.75	26000	5.4	130	22.09
NOR4	1474	213.2	1324.96	87.75	73051	5.4	120	21.87
NOR5	1463	213.2	1293.6	238.75	68302	16.1	224	20.43
NOR6	1474	213.2	1277.92	186	18853	5.32	250	29.52
NOR7	1474	213.2	1223.04	153	12584	5.32	286	28.6
NOR8	1474	213.2	1348.48	268.75	815396	5.32	302	13.55

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Annex 2b. Closure of coal plants in coastal regions in the period 2019-2023.

Coal plant	Coastal Province	Region	POEM subd.	MW lost	Operator	Year of closure
<i>Litoral de Almería</i>	Almería	Andalucía	ESAL_1_2	1159	Endesa	2021
<i>de Puente Nuevo</i>	Córdoba	Andalucía	ESAL_1_2	324	Viesgo	2020
<i>de Los Barrios</i>	Cádiz	Andalucía	ESAL_1_2	589	EDP	2022
<i>de Lada</i>	Principality of Asturias		NOR_6_7_8	358	Iberdrola	2020
<i>del Narcea</i>	Principality of Asturias		NOR_6_7_8	530	Naturgy	2020
<i>de Aboño</i>	Principality of Asturias		NOR_6_7_8	916	EDP HC Energía	2022
<i>de Soto de Ribera</i>	Principality of Asturias		NOR_6_7_8	350+866	EDP HC Energía	2022
<i>de Es Murterar</i>	Baleares	Baleares	LEBA_2_3	260+75	Endesa	2019 & 2026
<i>de Serchs</i>	Barcelona	Catalunia	LEBA_1	162	E.ON	2011
<i>Puentes de G. Rodríguez</i>	La Coruña	Galicia	NOR_2_3_4	1468	Endesa	2023
<i>de Meirama</i>	La Coruña	Galicia	NOR_2_3_4	557	Naturgy	2020

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Asturias: <https://elperiodicodelaenergia.com/edp-adelanta-el-cierre-de-sus-centrales-de-carbon-en-espana-y-portugal-por-el-precio-del-co2/>;
<https://elpais.com/sociedad/2020-06-28/espana-desconecta-siete-termicas-y-arranca-el-proceso-para-enterrar-el-carbon.html>;
 Andalucía: https://www.europasur.es/los_barrios/Viesgo-central-termica_0_1509749328.html; <https://elpais.com/sociedad/2020-06-28/espana-desconecta-siete-termicas-y-arranca-el-proceso-para-enterrar-el-carbon.html>; <https://elperiodicodelaenergia.com/adios-agridulce-de-la-central-termica-de-carboneras/>;
 Balearic Islands: <https://www.lavanguardia.com/local/baleares/20191230/472609170402/la-central-termica-de-es-murterar-cierra-sus-dos-unidades-mas-contaminantes.html>
 Galicia: <https://elpais.com/sociedad/2020-06-28/espana-desconecta-siete-termicas-y-arranca-el-proceso-para-enterrar-el-carbon.html#>;
<https://elperiodicodelaenergia.com/endesa-desconecta-la-central-de-as-pontes-y-deja-espana-con-solo-2-gw-de-carbon/>;
 Catalonia: <https://www.lavanguardia.com/local/bergueda/20140923/54415908211/central-termica-cercs-investigacion-renovables.html>

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Annex 2c. Number of species, sensitivity scores according to stressors from EIONET Report (Korpinen et al., 2019)⁶¹. The report differs among score for the Atlantic Ocean (OWE-HPA located in CAN and NOR) and for the Mediterranean Sea (OWE-HPA located in ESAL and LEBA).

HPA-OWE	E_{fj}			S_i																	
	Number of species			Disturbance of species due to human presence			Disturbance of seabed			Physical loss of seabed			Change in hydrodynamic regime			Noise			Invasive species		
	nr_mammal	nr_fish	nr_birds	Fish	Mammals	Birds	Fish	Mammals	Birds	Fish	Mammals	Birds	Fish	Mammals	Birds	Fish	Mammals	Birds	Fish	Mammals	Birds
CANFV1	28	153	107	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
CANFV2	28	153	107	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
CANGC1	28	153	112	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
CANLANZ1	28	154	105	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
CANTEN1	27	153	116	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
CANTEN2	27	153	116	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
ESAL1	17	167	231	3.5	3.25	5	4	1.88	5	3.5	0.16	3	3.5	1.63	2.5	4	4.88	4	4	0.5	1
ESAL2	12	166	201	3.5	3.25	5	4	1.88	5	3.5	0.16	3	3.5	1.63	2.5	4	4.88	4	4	0.5	1
LEBA1	12	150	218	3.5	3.25	5	4	1.88	5	3.5	0.16	3	3.5	1.63	2.5	4	4.88	4	4	0.5	1
LEBA2	12	140	139	3.5	3.25	5	4	1.88	5	3.5	0.16	3	3.5	1.63	2.5	4	4.88	4	4	0.5	1
LEBA3	12	139	139	3.5	3.25	5	4	1.88	5	3.5	0.16	3	3.5	1.63	2.5	4	4.88	4	4	0.5	1
NOR1	27	148	173	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
NOR2	26	138	172	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
NOR3	26	134	171	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
NOR4	26	134	169	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
NOR5	26	133	165	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
NOR6	26	134	163	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
NOR7	26	134	156	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1
NOR8	26	134	172	2	2.88	3	1	0.04	0.03	2	1.50	0.81	2	0.03	1	2.5	3.75	2	1.5	0	1

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Annex 2d. Number of habitats (Ef_j), summed habitat sensitivity scores (S_i) according to stressors from EIONET Report (Korpinen et al., 2019)⁶¹.

	Ef_j		S_i						
	Nr of different habitats	SUM_Physical loss of seabed	SUM_Disturbance due to human presence	SUM_Change in hydrodynamic regime	SUM_Input of hazardous substances	SUM_noise	SUM_invasive_species	$\sum S_i$	$R_{HPA-OWE}$
HPA-OWE									
CANFV1	2	4.0	3.0	3.5	3.0	0.8	4.0	18.3	36.5
CANFV2	1	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.3	2.0	7.3	7.3
CANGC1	2	4.0	3.0	3.5	3.0	0.8	4.0	18.3	36.5
CANLANZ1	2	4.0	3.0	3.5	3.0	0.8	4.0	18.3	36.5
CANTEN1	3	7.0	7.0	7.5	6.0	1.3	7.0	35.8	107.3
CANTEN2	1	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.3	2.0	7.3	7.3
ESAL1	1	0.0	2.5	3.0	1.0	0.3	0.0	6.8	6.8
ESAL2	1	0.0	2.5	3.0	1.0	0.3	0.0	6.8	6.8
LEBA1	3	2.0	7.5	10.0	6.0	0.8	2.0	28.3	84.8
LEBA2	3	5.0	8.0	10.5	6.0	1.4	2.0	32.9	98.6
LEBA3	3	3.0	7.5	10.0	5.0	1.1	2.0	28.6	85.9
NOR1	3	6.0	7.0	8.0	3.0	1.5	6.0	31.5	94.5
NOR2	3	6.0	4.0	6.0	3.0	1.3	6.0	26.3	78.8
NOR3	3	6.0	7.0	6.0	3.0	1.3	6.0	29.3	87.8
NOR4	3	6.0	7.0	6.0	3.0	1.3	6.0	29.3	87.8
NOR5	5	10.0	9.0	11.5	5.0	2.3	10.0	47.8	238.8
NOR6	4	9.0	11.5	10.0	5.0	2.0	9.0	46.5	186.0
NOR7	4	8.0	8.0	8.5	4.0	1.8	8.0	38.3	153.0
NOR8	5	11.0	12.0	12.0	5.5	2.3	11.0	53.8	268.8

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Annex 3. MSE scores for the 13 criteria per planning subdivision and planning tier.

X.IncMSE	Criteria	C-Cost/B-Benefit	Subdivision	Planning Tier
14.41	MPA_5km_buffer_n	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Spatial-Efficiency
15.06	MPA_5km_buffer_.	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Spatial-Efficiency
18.98	CR_Ix	Cost	Canary Islands	Spatial-Efficiency
19.39	MP_perc	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Spatial-Efficiency
19.56	Depth_m	Cost	Canary Islands	Technical/Technological
20.84	Decarbonization_lostMW	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Energy-Equity
20.98	Reg_contr_perc	Cost	Canary Islands	Energy-Equity
22.86	Riskmammals_Idx	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Socio-Ecological
23.31	Gov_perc	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Spatial-Efficiency
25.05	GDPpercapita	Benefit	Straight-Alborán	Energy-Equity
25.17	Tourist_press_touristper1kinh	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Socio-Ecological
25.17	Decarbonization_lostMW	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Energy-Equity
25.72	Tourist_press_touristper1kinh	Cost	Canary Islands	Socio-Ecological
26.71	Substrate_suit_perc	Benefit	North Atlantic	Technical/Technological
27.15	CR_Ix	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Spatial-Efficiency
27.37	Reg_contr_perc	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Energy-Equity
27.38	mean_Fish_effort_hours	Cost	North Atlantic	Spatial-Efficiency
27.79	Riskmammals_Idx	Cost	Canary Islands	Socio-Ecological
29.09	Constrain_n	Cost	North Atlantic	Spatial-Efficiency
29.38	Decarbonization_lostMW	Cost	North Atlantic	Energy-Equity
29.65	Pop_n	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Socio-Ecological
29.93	Tourist_press_touristper1kinh	Cost	North Atlantic	Socio-Ecological
30.82	Install_Cap_MW	Benefit	Levantine-Balearic	Energy-Equity
30.86	MPA_5km_buffer_.	Cost	Canary Islands	Spatial-Efficiency
31.32	RiskBirds_Idx	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Socio-Ecological
32.64	Tourist_employment	Cost	North Atlantic	Socio-Ecological
32.88	Energy_bal_Idx	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Energy-Equity
33.22	MeanWaveHeight_m	Cost	North Atlantic	Technical/Technological
35.22	Substrate_suit_perc	Benefit	Levantine-Balearic	Technical/Technological
36.96	Decarbonization_lostMW	Cost	Canary Islands	Energy-Equity
40.17	MP_perc	Cost	Canary Islands	Spatial-Efficiency
41.47	Energy_bal_Idx	Cost	North Atlantic	Energy-Equity

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42.16	Re_energy_perc	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Energy-Equity
42.43	RiskHabitats_Idx	Cost	Canary Islands	Socio-Ecological
42.78	Riskfish_Idx	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Socio-Ecological
44.05	Distance_km	Benefit	North Atlantic	Socio-Ecological
47.38	Storms_Idx	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Technical/Technological
51.36	CR_Ix	Cost	North Atlantic	Spatial-Efficiency
51.66	RiskBirds_Idx	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Socio-Ecological
59.00	RiskHabitats_Idx	Cost	North Atlantic	Socio-Ecological
59.31	Distance_km	Benefit	Canary Islands	Socio-Ecological
61.47	Gov_perc	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Spatial-Efficiency
61.48	TP_x	Benefit	North Atlantic	Technical/Technological
63.04	Tourist_employment	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Socio-Ecological
63.62	MU_Idx	Benefit	Straight-Alborán	Technical/Technological
72.74	MU_Idx	Benefit	Canary Islands	Technical/Technological
73.76	Telecom_km	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Spatial-Efficiency
75.62	TP_x	Benefit	Canary Islands	Technical/Technological
76.62	MU_Idx	Benefit	North Atlantic	Technical/Technological
77.04	Substrate_suit_perc	Benefit	Canary Islands	Technical/Technological
85.12	MPA_5km_buffer_n	Cost	Levantine-Balearic	Spatial-Efficiency
87.59	Space_dem_perc	Cost	Straight-Alborán	Spatial-Efficiency

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735 Contributions

736 D.D. led the research project, conceived the research idea, defined the analysis principles,
737 collected and prepared the datasets, drafted and tested the code, prepared the manuscript and
738 the figures and tables (except Fig. 1); M.A. prepared and revised the R-code, supplied and

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739 revised the methodological description of the ensemble MCDA and random forest; S.R.
740 prepared the versioning of Fig.1, oversaw the preparation of indicators and the collection and
741 preparation of data on fish, birds and marine mammals distribution. J.S. contributed to the
742 analysis principles and reviewed and commented the manuscript; C.M.L. co-lead the research
743 project, contributed to the definition of the analysis principles and reviewed the manuscript.